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Leveraging Transfer Learning from Indian Patient Metadata for Deep Learning-Based Chest X-ray Interpretation

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Abstract:

Deep learning methods have become very popular as AI has improved. They are used to make strong classification models that work well in many areas, such as medical diagnosis jobs. It is suggested in this study that the CNN model (Convolutional Neural Network) be used to sort Chest Radiological Society of North America (RSNA) Pneumonia databases with X-ray pictures. The study also tries to try out different ways to get the same RSNA test results with the limited computing power techniques to the methods that have been used in

[1]

the last few years. What the suggested method is based on a CNN that isn't too complicated and the use of transfer learning algorithms like Xception and Inception V3/V4. NetB7 is efficient. The study also tries to get the same RSNA standard scores using the limited computer resources by trying out different ways to use the methods that have already been put in place in the last few years. RSNA's standard MAP score is 0.25, but when the Mask RCNN model is used on A randomly chosen group of 3017 Indian people and picture enhancement led to a MAP score of 0.15. At the same time, the YoloV3 the MAP score was 0.32 when no hyperparameters were tuned, but the loss keeps going down. Running if you run the model more times, you might get better results.

1. Introduction:

Poisoning is the most common cause of death for kids under five. World-wide, more than 15% of all deaths in children under five are caused by pneumonia. Researchers worked on using deep learning methods to identify pneumonia from chest X-rays because it can be caused by viruses, bacteria, or fungus. In the United States in 2015, pneumonia was one of the top ten reasons of death, with more than 500,000 visits to emergency rooms and more than 50,000 deaths as a result. Medicine and care that are cheap and don't use a lot of technology can be used to treat illness that is simply avoided.

Diagnose pneumonia takes a long time and requires highly skilled professionals who look at a chest X-ray or scan and then confirm the diagnosis with a patient's medical history, vital signs, and lab tests.

Infections in the lungs can be found and measured by doctors using this information [1]. According to X-ray, respiratory sickness looks like a region of increased opacity. Identifying respiratory disease on a chest X-ray is hard because the lungs can look cloudy for many reasons, including cancer, bleeding, pulmonary oedema, and more. Finding pneumonia is easier when chest X-rays are taken at regular times and compared to the patient's symptoms.

Utilising a focused beam of radiation, a chest X-ray checks your heart, lungs, and bones. No pain or discomfort is involved in chest X-rays. X-ray readings are usually available in one to two days. An earlier diagnosis can make sure that people

get care on time and save much-needed time and money. An X-ray of the chest uses directed beams of radiation. Your body's insides are shown on these radiation beams. The negative images of black-and-white photos look like X-ray shots. You have different tissue thicknesses. Radiation passes through different parts of your body at different rates. Bones, for example, are very thick and don't let much radiation through. In an X-ray, bones look like they are white. Although, your lungs let 2 more rays through [2]. An X-ray of your lungs shows that they are not coloured. Healthcare professionals look at the colours and colouring on an X-ray to find and treat health problems.

A medical worker snaps chest X-rays. They specialise in X-ray tests. This makes it harder to understand because the CXR's look changes depending on things like the patient's position and the amount of inspiration. Moreover, doctors have to read a lot of CXRs every day. If AI and ML are used to automate the initial discovery or picture screening of possible lung sickness cases to grade them and speed up their review, this repeated job and the need for highly skilled doctors can be reduced.

Because people's lives are at stake, making a program that can automatically tell if a patient has pneumonia or not without using an X-ray should be exceptionally accurate. In this research, we attempted to create a model that can identify and pinpoint the location of a pneumonia illness in the lungs. Using limited computer power, we've tried a number of different methods by downsampling, shrinking, and so on. In order to get the standard results, our study combines different approaches that produce more accurate pictures with fewer downsampled and shrunk ones. This way will allow us to test different ideas and get better outcomes with fewer computing resources and less data. Eventually, this will assist us in creating a more advanced computer vision program that eliminates the burden of computing resources.

2. Literature Review:

A severe chest virus can lead to pneumonia, a lung disease. Pulmonary asthma kills one out of every five children who die [1]. Annually, 1.5 million people in the US go to the emergency room with pneumonia as their main diagnosis (CDC, 2018). The second most deaths from pneumonia in children under five years old happened

in India in 2018. About 153,000 children died in their first month, which is when most of the deaths happened. Medication and care that are cheap and don't require a lot of technology can help avoid it and treat it. After getting a chest X-ray, pneumonia is generally proven. It aids medical professionals in figuring out the size and location of the problem. For some lung illnesses, an X-ray may show a region of increased reflectivity [2]. This is because different conditions, like cancer, bleeding, pulmonary swelling, and others, can show up as opacities in the lungs on a chest X-ray, making it hard to diagnose respiratory disease. Getting a patient's chest X-rays at regular times and comparing them to their symptoms can help locate pneumonia. What the CXR [3] looks like depends on things like how the patient is positioned and how deep the inspiration is, which makes it harder to read. Additionally, radiologists are responsible for analysing a large number of CXRs every day. By using AI and ML to handle the initial discovery or picture screening of possible lung illness cases, this repeated job and the need for highly skilled doctors can be cut down. In the medical field, most people use CNN's transfer learning method to classify data that they have access to. Thanks, Okeke S. and others [10] did a study on a large dataset that had the train, validation, and test sets, as well as two sub-folders with the Pneumonia and non-Pneumonia classes. Starting from scratch, the suggested model is made up of two parts: a feature generator and a classifier. For the pre-processing part, data addition was used. Multiple Conv. Maximising pooling and activating Relu on layers. Various output sizes were tried during the training phase and then put together to make a 1D feature for the classifier process. Dropout (0.5), two thick layers with Relu, and output with sigmoid activation were put in place while the algorithm was working. The end results showed that $(200 \times 200 \times 3)$ was the best picture shape, with a validation score of 94% and a loss of 0.18%. The study found that a smaller picture did better than a bigger one in terms of confirmation score. PAN et al. did a two-step classification [4]. Four transfer learning models that were learnt on ImageNet were used to classify the images. Two models were put together to perform object recognition. First, the picture was labelled as either positive or negative. Object scanners were used to make the line segments in the second stage. Positive pictures were used to train the object recognition model. Additionally, the metadata was added, but no useful conclusions for the model making were discovered. Several picture sizes (1024×1024) were tried after the original resolution (1024×1024) was lowered. No speed drop happened when training on images with a small quality. Separated into tenfolds, the statistics were also.

122.5 percent of the projected bounding box was cut down to make it more accurate on the test data. Researchers led by Cheng and others created a one-stage design that could both classify objects and find their locations within a bounding box [5]. At 224×224 , the X-rays' sharpness was lowered. Additions to the training dataset included random rotations, translations, scaling, horizontal shifting, and the addition or removal of random factors. The data set was split into a training set that was 95% and a confirmation set that was 5%. The pictures were sorted using RetinNet, which had already been trained on the ImageNet collection. Anwar H. and others wrote a study [11] using a COVID-CXNet to gather several datasets and combine them into one. Image enhancement, normalisation, and resizing to 320×320 were done during pre-processing, and CLAHE and BEASF were used to improve sharpness. Three kinds of experiments were done. The base model's simple architecture includes simple designs that don't have BN or Pooling. In the second experiment, ChexNet was built with DenseNet. In the third experiment, COVIDNet was set up using the CheXNet model as its supporting structure. It was graded using the Grad-Cam method. The main model got an AUC of 0.99, 98% accuracy, and an F1 score of 0.94. The results were also explained. The second experiment incorrectly predicted the outcome, leading to poor results; the third experiment, on the other hand, was 87.2% accurate. The study concluded that the suggested model improves performance and lowers overfitting. For the F1 score, it has a few good examples that tend to overfit. A group of researchers led by Joseph P. [12] created a model of COVID-19 pneumonia for a frontal chest X-ray tool that can be used to keep an eye on the disease without performing any invasive procedures. The research used two kinds of datasets: i) COVID-19 Cohort datasets and ii) Non-COVID-19 datasets, which combined different types of data like RSNA into one. Within the cohort dataset, unknown radiologists gathered data using the following scores: (1) ground-glass opacity/consolidation for specific lungs, where 0 meant no involvement and 1 through 4 meant involvement (with a total score between 0 and 8); and (2) degree of opacity for specific lungs, where 0 meant no opacity, 1 through 3 meant consolidation and white-out; and again, the total score between 0 and 6. The picture was resized to $[-1024, 1024]$ and formed into (224×224) . Due to its good performance in predicting Pneumonia disease, the study used a DenseNet model. Researchers tested four groups: middle feature, 18 outputs, 4 outputs, and lung opacity outputs. It was the simplest model (lung opacity) that got the highest score, followed by MAE-0.78 and MSE 0.86. Ultimately, the group came to the

conclusion that fewer traits and conditions are the most effective way to avoid overfitting. Therefore, the suggested model could be used for lowering and raising the level of stress, especially in the Intensive Care Unit (ICU). Hector Alberto S. using CXR pictures, et al. [13] made an end-to-end model for finding COVID-19 patients' lungs. On the various datasets, the learnt model utilised poorly guided learning techniques such as segmentation, score estimation, and spatial alignment. Therefore, the study showed the BS-Net model, which is very good at all, steps of pre-processing. The group gathered various types of datasets, including those from Montgomery Country, Shenzhen Hospital, the JSRT database, Brixia COVID-19, and the public COVID-19. At the application stage, backbone models from various designs such as ResNet, VGG, DenseNet, and Inception were utilised. The U-Net++ design obtains the lung's form and edges in the alignment part of the segmentation part. The Ensemble Decision Strategy (EDS) was used along with the Brixia prediction scores. The final numbers were 0.041 and 0.0424 for the mean and standard deviation. According to the study, acceptance numbers are either +/- 0.5 for the clinical perspective or +/- 2 for the world perspective. Eventually, the model got the features of stability and passed the performance test for accuracy and consistency. It is possible to diagnose X-ray vision more accurately with deep learning's picture processing method. Rachna J. et al. [14] acquired a dataset from Kaggle that includes pictures of COVID-19 positive, normal, and pneumonia cases. Training: 5467 and validation: 965 parts of the sample have been separated. The input shaping ($128 \times 128 \times 3$) has been executed. It was worked on various types of design, including Inception V3, Xception, and ResNet. For picture enhancement during pre-processing to avoid over-fitting. During testing, it was discovered that a picture shape of 128 will make it learn faster and a shape of 256 will make it do well. Therefore, 256 input forms were used for Xception, Inception, and ResNeXt, and LeakyRelu was used as the activation function. The review used a rating report. As compared to the other models, Xception Net got a great score of 0.97. According to the study's conclusion, the model did well in tests, but this might be because it was over-fitted. To find out what the real accuracy is, it can be checked against the new public dataset. Earlier, the patients' chest X-rays showed problems that pointing to a COVID-19 infection. Using the idea explained above, Linda W. Others [15] showed a COVID-Net model that can find X-ray pictures. When making a dataset, several datasets were combined, such as the RSNA Pneumonia dataset, for the creation of the COVIDx dataset. These 13,975 CXR pictures are now available to

the public and are divided into three groups: 1) no infection, 2) non-COVID-19 infection, and 3) COVID-19 virus infection. “Pre-processing” involved cutting out 8% of the picture, and “image enhancement” included setting up translation (10%), rotation (10%), flip (15%), zoom (15%), shift (10%), and other operations. After learning from the ImageNet collection and the VGG and DenseNet architectures, the COVID-Net is created. Furthermore, Adam was used as an optimiser, and the hyper-parameters were learning = $2e-4$, epochs = 22, factor = 0.7, and patience = 5. The study also used heterogeneous convolutional layers and kernels ranging from 1 to 7. The outcomes demonstrate that the COVID-Net design works better than the other models. It’s 93.3% accurate and 91% sensitive. As a result, the team has decided that this design is clearer, more reliable, and still allows for quick review. Xiaodong W. Others [16] came up with a way to make X-ray image findings easier. As a first step in the trial, data were gathered using five different transfer learning methods: Xception, VGG16, Inception V3, ResNet50, and DenseNet121. Afterward, the group suggested a way to make the test more accurate and useful. An end-to-end model is made by combining neural networks and machine learning. They used a re-sampling method to fix the imbalance problem after combining the samples. Before processing, the input form is set to 224×224 , and the picture is boosted and made normal between -1 and 1 to avoid over-fitting. The first model that is used is custom transfer learning. As a result, the second method is used on the bottleneck feature. This time, the pre-trained model is used to remove the features, which creates a lower-dimensional vector that saves time. Specific hyper-parameters were used during training: learning rate = $1e-7$, epochs = 1000, and batch size = 32. As a result, the COVID-19 pictures were forecast by machine learning methods (DT, RF, AdaBoost, Bagging, and SVM) using the saved bottleneck feature as input. The review used Sensitivity, Specificity, and Accuracy. The results for the base model-Xception design were 94.16% sensitivity, 99.17% specificity, 96.38% F1, and 96.54% AUC. The best model by combining bottleneck methods was Xception + SVM. This model showed that it was sensitivity (97.27%), specificity (99.38%), F1 (96.63%), and AUC (96.77%). Therefore, the researcher comes to the conclusion that using both deep learning and machine learning together works better than using only one or the other. Common modern ways to diagnose diseases include X-ray imaging techniques and antigen/ molecular tests for finding out how bad the disease is and whether it is present. A lot of what is used to identify the people depends on their age. Nevertheless, a number of models were trained on the RSNA

dataset, which mainly includes pictures of children. Therefore, these models might give wrong information about some cases of the disease. As a result, Julian D. these authors [17] suggested the case study as a way to show how much work goes into pre-processing to get correct results. They also compared it to other models. It was studied using two sets of XR images: Posterior Anterior and Anterior-Posterior. This data set is split into three parts: normal, pneumonia, and COVID-19. Image pre-processing turned XR pictures into uncompressed 16-bit PNG files, which were then put through the Monochrome 2 filter without losing any of the features. COVID-Net is the model that is being suggested. It was shrunk to $224 \times 224 \times 3$ pixels and normalised with a mean of $[0.485, 0.456, 0.456]$ and a standard deviation of $[0.229, 0.224, 0.225]$ using the Z Score tool. Implemented hyper-parameters were $lr = 2e-5$, epochs = 24, batch-size = 32, factor = 0.5, and patience = 3. Image enhancement (flip), Gaussian noise + variance (0.015), and scale were all used. Later, Relu and dropout (0.3) were added to the FC layers' first step. All three types of methods were used. One way uses only raw data, with the original size and without any editing or addition. The second way started with pre-processing the data by zooming, cutting, and shrinking it into a square picture with a ratio of 1:1. It's mostly filtering that separates the lungs from the U-Net segments. Last, greyscale was added to both the vertical and horizontal lines. That tells us the squared area of the lungs and uses it to make a normal distribution. The last method was very similar to the second way. One extra seed (5×5) was added to make it bigger and placed on top of the chest area. Therefore, method 1 works better, with an AUC of 0.99 and a world performance accuracy of 91%. Both methods 2 and 3 did not work as well as method 1, with ROC values between 81% and 93% and a world performance accuracy of 87%. Finally, method 3 has a slightly lower COVID-19 class than method 2. Although it got a world score of 0.98%, it has 224, 316 X-ray scans of 65, 240 patients, and each report were marked with 14 observations as positive, negative, or uncertain. The expert dataset by the Stanford ML Group has been used in a number of empirical studies. For better handling of unclear observations that make up a big part of many CXR datasets, Yuan et al. (2020) suggested using the label smoothing method, which is also used in Z. For example, Yuan et al., in the reasoning stage, Test-Time Augmentation (TTA) and data augmentation were used for each CXR. The model was taught using a various transfer learning method, and it was noticed that various classifiers give every name a different score. To get a very good predictor, an ensemble method is therefore looked into. It utilised six

different architectures: DenseNet-121, DenseNet-169, DenseNet-201, Inception-ResNet-v2, Exception, and NASNetLarge. All of the above-trained networks' output was collected to make the ensemble model, which had an AUC score of 0.930 for [6] H.H. Pham et al. (2019). With the goal of raising the AUC score, Z suggested using an AUC margin-based substitute loss function. According to Yuan et al. (2020) instead of the commonly used AUC square loss, DAM was trained in two stages. The first stage focused on learning by improving the normal cross-entropy loss on various transfer learning algorithms, such as DenseNet-121, DenseNet-161, DensNet-169, DensNet-201, and Inception-ResNet-v2. In the second stage, the goal is to maximise AUC by fine-tuning the classifier's decision limit and decreasing the AUC margin loss. Training weights for the last classifier layer in the first stage are changed to random weights, and the DAM method is used to make the last classifier layer and all the layers before it work better. Later, an AUC score of 0.9305 was reached, which means Z. Topping the Chex pert challenge is the work of Yuan et al. (2020) [7]. Along with other researchers, Mohammad Farukh Hashmi and others [18] tested their ideas on a huge collection of 5858 labelled Optical Coherence Tomography (OCT) and chest X-ray pictures [8]. Multiple doctors marked the dataset, and then another doctor looked it over and gave feedback. The training set had 5156 pictures, and the test set had 700 images. Anyone who has viral or bacterial pneumonia is considered to have pneumonia. These two additions (normal/no pneumonia) get rid of any uneven data in the training set. Because each neural network's design specifies a different picture size, the photos were adjusted to 224*224 and 229*229. There are 5 types in total. A weighted sum was used to classify after ResNet-18, DenseNet-121, MobileNet-V2, Inception-V3, and Exception were trained separately. For better generalisation, SGD was used as the optimiser [9], and the model was trained for 25 iterations. With values of 0.001, 0.9, and 0.0001, the learning rate, momentum, and weight decline were set. Case 1: Each model made an equal contribution to the end results; specifically 0.20 weight was given to each design. A test result of 97.45% correctness and a loss of 0.087 were found. By figuring out the best weights for each design based on how well it classified, we were able to make a final weighted classifier that had an AUC of 99.76 and a testing accuracy of 98.43. I.M. Researchers led by E.H. Chowdhury [19] did tests on both deep networks and shallow networks, including ResNet-101, VGG-19, DenseNet-201, CheXNet, and InceptionV3. For example, for Squeeze Net, the images were resized to 227×227 pixels, for InceptionV3, they were resized

to 299×299 pixels, and for mobilenet-V2, ResNet-18, ResNet-101, VGG-19, and DenseNet-201, they were resized to 224×224 pixels. According to Case1, COVID-19 chest X-ray pictures were much lower than 423; images were down sampled to even out features; then, to balance the data, equal samples were randomly chosen from 1579 people who were healthy and 1485 people who had viral pneumonia. For case 2, all CXR pictures were used, including 423 COVID-19 images, 1579 normal images, and 1485 images of viral pneumonia. Some traits were not evenly distributed, so COVID-19 images were increased six folds while normal and viral pneumonia images were only increased once to keep the balance between the groups. We tested each study using a stratified 5-folds cross-validation with 80:20 training: testing ratio. Ten percent of the training data was used as a validation set to check the hyper-parameter and avoid over fitting.

3. Data & Pre-processing:

Back in 1999, Daffner said that the chest X-ray was a “mirror of health and disease.” How about this? The chest X-ray is still the most common test done in radiology offices, even though it’s been 211 years since Daffner’s comment in 1999 [Bundesamt für Strahlenschutz, 2020; NHS England, 2020]. Readers can learn how to read chest X-rays and spot problems in books by Brant et al. (2023), Lange et al. (2023), and Darby et al. (2022). A chest X-ray shows parts of the body below, along with some names used in chest radiography.

They get their names from the way the X-ray beam goes through the body. It is common to group them into three types: posteroanterior (PA), lateral, and anteroposterior (AP) projections. Two of the most important exams of the thorax are shown in Fig. (a) and (b). These are the side and PA exams. Patients must be standing up straight in order for a PA check to be done. Put your hands on your hips or the bars of the machine, and then press the front of your chest against them. This makes the radiation rays go from the front of the chest to the back of the body, which is called the rear area. The patient is standing with his arms raised and his left side facing the camera, according to Lange et al. (2023). It’s common to give AP tests to people who can’t stand or are stuck in bed. The patient presses on the monitor with his back chest instead of his breasts like PA does. That is, the beam of energy goes through the middle part of the patient’s chest, where the front and back meet. Because of this, the X-ray picture is bigger because there is more room between the organs and the screen.

(a) Frontal Part chest X-ray

(b) Lateral Part chest X-ray

Fig. 1

X-rays of the chest are also hard to understand because they are projections. The main reason for this is that sickness and changes in the body often happen at the same time. It can also be hard to tell the difference between diseases or structures that look alike but are not (for example, invasion and normal blood flow structure in the lungs). Radiologists usually look at a lot of chest X-rays to better understand them and get better at making decisions once they know the basics of how to do it. A lung X-ray of a healthy person looks a certain way after many years of practice. They then look at this picture and compare each new case to it. Because this is a subjective process, there are often big differences between and within doctors who look at chest X-rays [Albaum et al., 2016; Johnson et al., 2020]. Image systems are said to have spatial clarity when they can tell the difference between two things that are very close to each other. Our eyes see fuzzy images when they don't have good spatial clarity. There are two functions, line spread and modulation transfer that can be used to check how sharp a picture system is. These steps will work. Take a picture of a thin line (or slit) in space that is a certain size before you can use the line spread feature. Also, we need to know how wide this line is at half of its widest point before we can figure out how fuzzy it is. Two different measured cuts can be used to get exact values for both the Fourier transformation and the modulation transfer function, as explained in the paper by Sawant et al. (2023). You could do this with the same cut.

220 Philips Healthcare phone number on the newest chest X-rays, the active picture area is 34 to 42 centimetres wide, and the spatial precision is 3.4 line

pairs per millimetre. What this says is that the picture is generally 2000 to 3000 pixels wide. Since the picture spot is already being used, this has to be done. So that they can tell the difference between the small signs of different lung diseases [Huda et al., 2015], radiologists need to be very good at figuring out where things are in space. This part of the shot can be used to get a full ultrasound of the chest. It is important to see a doctor right away because a pneumothorax is one of the most dangerous things that can be seen on a chest X-ray. Since the edge of the pleura is almost invisible on a high-resolution X-ray, it is not easy to see. One good X-ray of the lungs is shown in Figure (a). Both its width and height are 2828 pixels. The picture has been made ten times bigger in two specific places, as shown in Figure (b). The blue and red boxes show these spots. You can find them by following the yellow lines.

The pleura edge can be seen in this shot, which shows that there is a pneumothorax. If the spatial sharpness wasn't good enough, this line would be fuzzy and the words would not be clear. CNNs that take in data that are between 224 and 299 pixels square are usually used by computer vision to separate parts of a picture. This is true according to some experts, like He et al. (2015). [Bar et al., 2015; Rajpurkar et al., 2017; Yao et al., 2017] are some new works that you might want to think about. For the source picture to fit the input size, bilinear interpolation is often used to shrink it. This is done to fix the fact that the picture sent in was not the same size as the original. Some parts of the picture, like the edge of the pleura, might be harder to see when the image is shrunk in this way. The space is not as sharp now because of this change. One bad thing that happens with this kind of downscaling is shown in Part (c) of Figure 2.3. Bilinear interpolation can be used to reduce the size of the chest X-ray from 2828×2320 pixels to 256×256 pixels. From left to right, the picture is 11 times smaller and 9 times smaller.

Fig. 2, A comparison between a chest X-ray with high and low clarity using a pneumothorax. For example, (a) displays the original chest X-ray with a resolution of 2828×2320 pixels. A ten-fold increase is shown in (b) for two parts of (a). The pneumothorax is shown by the yellow lines pointing to the edge of the pleura. Comparatively, (c) displays (a) that has been shrunk by bilinear interpolation to a 256×256 pixel picture. In (d), the pleura edge is no longer visible, but the same places have been enlarged as in (b).

4. Methodology:

4.1. Overview:

Literature review and analysis of all the available data were the first parts of the study. To make a basic CNN model, the conclusions drawn from the data and poll were used. The study now looks at transfer learning models after looking at the basic CNN model. Because the imagenet weights were already learnt, they were only used on the transfer learning model layers. With input pictures that were shrunk to 224×224 , three different transfer learning models were learnt on 3017 sorted samples. It was later tried with max vote with a group of three transfer learning models. Not only were the findings good, but they only fixed half of our problem. In light of this, we switched to more complex computer vision methods, such as masked RCNN. Our goals were met by this.

4.2. CNN:

The binary classification of X-rays for the base model was done with a CNN design. Prior to working with the data, the copies were taken out. Following the removal of copies, there were 26684 unique X-rays left. Moreover, the class names were written by hand. Entries that did not have lung opacity or were normal were given a score of 0, and entries that did have lung opacity were listed as 1. Later, the first class group was taken away. The results were then divided using Cochran's method. This made a total of 2203 X-rays, with 1707 negative labels and 496 positive labels. After the data was separated into layers, the 2203 X-rays were taken out of the main collection. This data was taken from the photos using the pydicom tool and then turned into pixel arrays so they could be processed further. Using this information, the chest X-ray grid had to look like this: (2203, 1024, 1024). The matching labels were taken out for the same 2203 cases. To make dealing with CNN design easier, the label matrix was changed to have the shape (2203, 1, 1).

Fig. 3: CNN Architecture

The chest X-ray matrix's pixel information was checked, and the lowest and highest numbers were found to be 255 and 0, respectively. Later, the pictures were shrunk from 1024 pixels to 224 pixels. The skimage library's resize method was used for this. The highest and lowest numbers of pixels changed after shrinking to one thousand and zero. Then, 30% of the data was split between train and test. For the CNN method to work with the X_train and X_test, they were changed to (1542, 224, 224, 1) and (661, 224, 224, 1), respectively. The base model design had 5 Max Pooling layers and 5 Convolutional layers. The 16th and 32nd convolutional layers had size (3, 3) filters, respectively. Whereas the last three convolutional layers had 64 filters of size (3, 3). Each convolutional layer used the Relu activation function. It was set to (2, 2) for the Max Pooling layers. As the last Max Pooling layer finished, the output was smoothed so that it could be used as an input by fully connected layers. The neural network had 512 neurones and a Relu activation function. For binary classification, the last output layer had one neurone with a sigmoid activation function.

The RSNA dataset has labels that are very uneven when the EDA is being done. As a result, the downsample method was used. The third label on the RSNA dataset, which said "No opacity/normal," was taken away for this experiment. You use the replies to save the best model with val_accuracy and lower the learning rate measures.

4.3.1. The Model I:

1. The first model's job is to use the chest X-ray to find pneumonia.
2. The project uses two different CNN transfer learning models: ResNet50 and InceptionV4 (Modified).
3. The models had a form of 224×224 , used only Imagenet weights in ResNet50, and had a unique top layer with 20% dropout and Global Average Pooling.
4. 20 epochs for ResNet50, 30 epochs for InceptionV4, 64 batch sizes, sigmoid activation, and the Adam optimiser with the default learning rate.

4.3.2. The Model II:

1. First, the second model is for testing, and its goal is to find the chest's view point (PA-AP).
2. The RSNA dataset is used to train this model, and its test data is used to make sure it works.
3. The AP-PA parts in the EDA are also not balanced, just like they were in model I. To fix this, the downsample method was used to make the features equal.
4. This model is used on the EfficientNetB0 transfer learning model.
5. The same values and hyper-parameters are used as in Model I.

4.3.3. The Model III:

1. The third model's job is to use the clahe filter to find pneumonia.
2. This model is trained on a tweaked version of InceptionNetV4 that doesn't have any pre-trained weights. It has a form of 224×224 , a top layer called Global Average Pooling, and a dropout value of 0.25.
3. Model II's values and hyper-parameters are very similar to these ones.

4.4. Mask R-CNN:

The next step after Faster RCNN is Mask RCNN. It has an extra Segmentation Mask for each item that it finds. There is also an FCN that takes a ROI as input and suggests a segmentation mask. This FCN is used for object recognition and localisation.

1. The Matterport version of Mask R-CNN was used to run Mask RCNN on the RSNA dataset. Resnet50 and Resnet101 were both used as backbones. As well as picture enhancement, the image's measurements were shrunk to (256, 256). A Jupyter setup with Tensor Flow-GPU turned on was used to train the model.

2. To start, a sorted sample of 3017 pictures were used to train and test the model. With a learning rate of 0.06, Model I was set up for 16 points. More information was learnt faster in the first two epochs. At last, 200 steps were added to each layer to train it.
3. Third, using stratified selection, the number of pictures for Model II was raised to 4836. For this model, image enhancement wasn't used. I used a resnet50 backbone to train the model. When the pictures were made bigger, loss went down.
4. Resnet101 was changed to be the backbone for Model III. There was even less change in ranking after this.
5. In the end, 9068 pictures were added as models for Model IV. It gets worse at finding bounding boxes as the number of pictures goes up, though, and the loss goes up to 0.5216.

4.5. Yolo V3:

The letters YOLO stand for "You only look once." A real-time object recognition method, this CNN design is known to be faster than others that are close. Despite this, the accuracy of the recognition is kept. The Yolo design partitions a picture into several areas. Within each part of the picture, the surrounding boxes and their chances of happening are forecast. We learnt an RSNA dataset version of Yolo v3. The main feature collector for the Yolo v3 design is Darknet-53. This backbone works better than others like Resnet101. The model only learnt from pictures of pneumonia. The training set had 5410 pictures, and the confirmation set had 602. The information was transformed using image enhancement. 0.001 was used as the learning rate. For 900 iterations, the model was put together. Building the model took six hours on a six-gigabyte GPU.

Fig. 4: Yolo V3 Structure

5. Results:

a. Early Results:

Binary cross-entropy was used as the loss function when the model was put together. An optimiser called RMSProp was used, and it learnt at a rate of 0.001. The thing that was used to judge was accuracy. A batch size of 16 and 25 epochs were used to fit the model. For the fit, the confirmation data was also given. To make things go faster, the model was run on a 17-Jupyter system based on a GPU. At the end of the 25th epoch, the train accuracy was 95% and the confirmation accuracy was 79%.

b. Interim Findings:

The simple model is too good at fitting, as shown above. So, three transfer learning models with a learning rate of 0.0001 tried different things to avoid or get better at overfitting. Not a single hyper-parameter was changed besides the learning rate. It tried Xception, Inception V3, and EfficientNetB7 as transfer learning models. All 30 epochs of batch size 128 were tested, and 5 patience were used to stop the process early.

Table 1: Transfer learning results

Sr. No.	Model Name	Training Accuracy	Validation Accuracy
1.	Xception	77.14%	75.87%
2.	InceptionV3	75.97%	73.77%
3.	EfficientB7	75.07%	75.76%

c. Final Results:

i. Model 1:

ResNet50 got a training score of 92%, validation score of 90% while InceptionV4 got a training score of 96% and a validation score of 94%.

**Fig. 5: a. Lung Opacity was Actual, Normal was Predicted (ResNet50);
b. Normal was seen, and normal was expected (InceptionNetv4).**

ii. Model 2:

This experiment works well with this model. With a loss of no more than 5%, this model has a validation score of 98.4%. It gets an AP grade of 98% and a PA grade of 99%. This model doesn't work well for classifying the finding of pneumonia.

Fig. 6: (a). Reality: PA, Expected Reality: PA; (b). Real: AP, Expected: AP

d. Mask R-CNN:

Separate calculations are being made for the costs for sorting and localisation. The loss for classification is based on binary cross-entropy, and the loss for localisation is based on the mean squared error of the box. The best results are seen in model 3, but model 1 has a MAP score of only 0.15. As you can see above, the model did well with a bounding box level of 0.1 for one of the cases. mAP was 0.32 in the end, which is higher than the top score of 0.25 in the RSNA competition.

Fig. 7: Results

6. Conclusion:

In our efforts to develop an efficient model that operates with minimal computational resources, we experimented with various models to generate faster and more accurate results, particularly in the computationally demanding domain of healthcare imaging. Our investigation led us to the YOLOv3 model, which, without any hyper-parameter tuning, produced results close to benchmark levels. This suggested potential for further optimization, as the model's loss continued to decrease with more iteration.

Key Reflections:

1. Limited data and a fixed learning rate constrained the model's ability to achieve higher accuracy.
2. Stratified sampling during training reduced the model's ability to learn critical features, especially since only one-third of the data represented the positive class.
3. Transfer learning with CNN methods might provide improved accuracy.
4. Implementing YOLOv3 effectively required fine-tuning and careful resource management.

Limitations:

Several limitations were identified in our approach:

1. Limited computational power restricted model performance.
2. Class imbalance, particularly with the "Not Normal/Pneumonia" class, led to classification issues.
3. The AP-PA model proved ineffective for pneumonia detection.
4. The CLAHE filter only improved results on pneumonia-positive X-rays, not on normal ones.
5. To manage memory, we had to configure batch sizes so that only one image was processed in the GPU per iteration.

6. At 900 iterations, the loss was still decreasing, indicating potential improvement with more iteration.
7. Running YOLOv3 without a GPU is infeasible.
8. The model might improve with image pre-processing and other image augmentation techniques.
9. The scaling down bounding box sizes could enhance accuracy.

This process highlighted the importance of understanding hyper-parameters, managing resources, and debugging. Basic CNN models showed promise for chest X-ray classification, but advanced architectures like YOLOv3 offer superior performance with proper resource management.

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